

Toward the Sea or the Land Cultural Identity and the Choice of Direction of Movement on the Water

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ABSTRACT

Archaeology, linguistics, and genetics have proved that Austronesian originated in mainland China. With the background of the spread of Austronesian from the southeastern coast of mainland China to the Pacific Ocean, this paper discusses the spatial movement characteristics of human beings from land to sea through their judgement of the natural environment in the non-navigational device era of 7,000-5,000 years ago. In terms of methodology, the optimal area of human movement from land to sea was modelled by means of a geographic information system (GIS). As a result, part of the movement area passed through the Liang Island, where human remains were found 8,400 years ago, thus increasing the validity of the method. The paper finally constructs a three-layer “land-coast-sea” movement model. By stripping away economic trade, science and technology, this paper provides a model of maritime mobility based on a purely “human-environmental” approach, which is a pathway to understanding the origins and dispersal of early human populations, a foundational scenario for further understanding of cultural identities and spatial activity, and a prerequisite for the construction of more complex maritime mobility.

Keywords: Maritime movement, Austronesian, Spatial analysis, Route Simulation, Cultural Landscape

Introduction

36 It is very interesting to find similar sites, totems, and languages on islands thousands of
37 kilometres apart. It seems as the sea was not exactly a hindrance, even before the advent of
38 machinery and modern navigation technology, the sea was not entirely a hindrance, but in a way
39 represented an abundance of resources, fast-passage routes (P. Bellwood 1979). Moving across
40 oceans is one way to explain the relationship between early human dispersal and the environment.
41 Understanding maritime movement is one way to understand the relationship between humans
42 and the environment. However, compared to land, the marine environment is complex and variable.

43 **Maritime movements without navigation equipment**

44 Air navigator Harold Charles Gatty published *The Raft Book* to provide navigation for airmen
45 flying across the Pacific during the World War II (Gatty 1999). The knowledge and methods
46 imparted are still useful today.

47 The theory which follows has also been practiced by the navigator Lewis, and he considers
48 that maritime movement is purposeful, technical, and methodical, not casual. Lewis in his 1964
49 article states the necessity of seafaring, which is not an accident but has a strong sense of
50 subjectivity. Voyaging is a major and uncertain undertaking, and there are a number of peoples
51 who have turned away from the sea and avoided sailing because of shipwrecks. The legendary
52 Tahitian navigator Rapa's father and uncle were separated from all of his crew on separate
53 voyages, and his mother appealed to him to avoid the sea (D. H. Lewis 1964) .

54 Beginning in 1966, David Lewis conducted experiments to test the theory of navigation at sea
55 proposed in 1964 (D. Lewis 1966). The voyage was accomplished using the old, non-navigational
56 equipment (with only chart sheets, South Pacific lifeboat charts, Raft Manual, star charts, solar
57 azimuths, astrological identification discs, and astrological notes). Birds were encountered during
58 the voyage (birds likewise provide a form of navigation; the direction in which a bird flies means
59 land; the type of bird on means to a different area). The sea voyage of more than 1,400 kilometres
60 was also successful, with a slight deviation in the middle of the road but not affecting the final
61 destination.

62 This allows us to discover, on the one hand, that navigation without navigational equipment
63 can be reproduced today, and on the other hand, it is a way to further understand the way ancient
64 humans moved through space in their environment.

65 **"Austronesian", one of the typical representatives of the maritime movement**

66 The origin and diffusion of Austronesian continues to attract the attention of scholars in
67 linguistics, archaeology, and genetics with many important discoveries updating the world's
68 knowledge of Austronesian time and time again.

69 Since the 16th century, explorers have found that the inhabitants of different islands in the
70 Pacific Ocean are not only extremely similar in appearance, but also almost identical in
71 pronunciation and meaning of many words, and thus the concept of "Austronesian" has entered
72 into the international academic. Austronesian, a concept extended from linguistic classification
73 (范志泉 2023), is now the only language family mainly distributed on islands and is one of the most
74 widely distributed language families in the world, including more than 1,200 languages and a
75 population of about 400 million speakers (郭健新, 邓晓华, and 王传超 2023). In terms of island
76 distribution, Austronesian extends from Madagascar in the west to Easter Island in the east, and
77 from Taiwan in China and the Hawaiian Islands in the north to the islands in the vast waters of
78 New Zealand in the south.

79 The origin and spread of Austronesian is an issue that has received the most attention at the
80 present time. In terms of origin, the theory that it originated on the south-east coast of mainland
81 China, passed through Taiwan and further spread to the Pacific islands is now more internationally
82 and nationally accepted. In terms of diffusion, the famous archaeologist Peter Bellwood put forward
83 the 'Express-Train Model' (J. M. Diamond 1988) (Figure 1), which suggests that Austronesian

84 spread to Polynesia at high speed after passing through the eastern part of Indonesia, and this
 85 has provided an important basis for later studies, and scholars from different disciplines have
 86 continuously verified the validity of this theory in different experiments. Scholars from different
 87 disciplines have also continuously verified the validity of this theory in different experiments.
 88 Nowadays, the origin and spread of Austronesian is still a hot topic of discussion worldwide.

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 90 **Figure 1 – Origin, Diffusion, and Express-Train Modelling of Austronesian (J. M. Diamond 1988)**
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92 **Recent Conjectures and Materials on Research of Austronesian**

93 *Archaeological Perspectives, Austronesian in Agro-Linguistic Co-Diffusion*

94 Archaeologists believe that early farmers who mastered the technology of rice domestication
 95 replaced hunter-gatherer languages and societies in their path of expansion (J. Diamond and
 96 Bellwood 2003). This is also reflected in the finding that, although humans may have arrived on
 97 some of the islands tens of thousands of years ago (Gibbons 2016), it was the arrival of
 98 Austronesian speakers that replaced the languages spoken on these islands (Figure 2).

99 Places such as the Yangtze River Delta are much richer in domesticable and highly successful
 100 wildlife species compared to other regions. Bellwood further noted in 2017 that domesticated
 101 wildlife species provide a stable resource (Figure 3), which in the case of the middle and lower
 102 reaches of the Yangtze River further shaped the largest population expansions, whose impacts
 103 ultimately affected distant islands thousands of years later (P. Bellwood 2017). But the question
 104 arises as to why people started farming if they could simply gather from the wild, and why did they
 105 move away from their homelands if they could farm?

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 107 **Figure 2 – Left: The first humans to spread from Southeast Asia to the Pacific (Gibbons 2016). Right: Archaeological Maps of Agricultural Homelands and**
 108 **Neolithic Formative Cultural Diffusion (J. Diamond and Bellwood 2003).**
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Figure 3 – Neolithic sites and early rice cultivation in southern China and Taiwan, with shaded area showing domesticated rice as early as 6000 BC (P. Bellwood 2017)

113 *Linguistic Perspectives, Austronesian - Zhuang Dong Integration*

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Linguistics contributes to the support of this study in two ways. On the one hand, the mutual validation of linguistic and archaeological models confirms the validity of the research methodology. Linguist Gray found through etymological analysis that the genealogical tree diagram of Austronesian is highly compatible with the 'Express Model', and can be converted into an ordered geographic character and mapped onto the genealogical tree of the languages (Gray and Jordan 2000). On the other hand, linguistics provides the hypothesis that there are two diffusion routes, land and sea, for Austronesian. Deng Xiaohua, a famous Chinese linguist, put forward the hypothesis that 'about 4000 years ago, the Sino-Tibetan language family and Austronesian began to separate and spread to Taiwan and the South Pacific Islands via the southeast coast or the southwest and south-central China Peninsula' by using the similarity matrix of cognates, the distance matrix, and the linguistic mathematical tree diagram (邓晓华 and 王士元 2003; 2007).

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This implies that in addition to the direction of diffusion of Austronesian from the southeast coast of China reaching Taiwan, China and spreading to the Pacific Ocean, there may have been a land direction of diffusion from Zhejiang, Fujian, and Vietnam to the Southeast Asian region. This provides important background support for this study.

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However, the etymological statistics method can only calculate an approximate time of language separation, a shortcoming that is also a fact that is now recognised by computational linguists, and therefore still needs to be mutually verified by different disciplines.

132 *Genetic Perspectives, Austronesian Surfacing with Genetic Technology Upgrades*

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In 1995, geneticists used a small segment of human leukocyte antigen for population clustering (Serjeantson et al. 1995), reflecting some of the expectations of archaeology (Bellwood 1989).

In 2005, Trejaut used haplogroup B4a1a as a tracer and found it to be widely distributed among the native inhabitants of Taiwan in China, Melanesians, and Polynesians (Trejaut et al. 2005).

In 2008, Friedlaender disagreed with the haplogroup B4a1a approach, and instead analysed 687 categories of genetic indicators, concluding that it suggests that Taiwan, and most likely the adjacent mainland China region, is the genetic birthplace of Austronesian, and that it supports the 'fast boat theory' (Friedlaender et al. 2008).

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In 2014, Ko and other scholars extracted DNA from human bones on Bright Island in the Matsu Archipelago, off the mouth of the Minjiang River in Fujian, suggesting that the early Austronesian left the southeastern coast of today's Fujian about 6,000 years ago, and that it left Taiwan about 4,000 years ago, spreading throughout the Southeast Asian islands, Madagascar, and Oceania (Ko et al. 2014).

146 In 2020, a breakthrough study by Chinese scientists on the origins of Chinese ethnic groups
147 showed that ancient populations in southern and northern China diverged as early as 9,500 years
148 ago, and that integration and communication occurred at least 8,300 years ago, suggesting that
149 the earliest Austronesian originated in Fujian and its neighbouring regions in southern China (Yang
150 et al. 2020). This is the first time that ancient genomic data have clearly demonstrated that the
151 ancient southern mainland populations of China more than 8,000 years ago were the ancestral
152 source of Austronesian.

153 Research Question

154 Bellwood's 1995 proposal of seven possible causes for the continued movement of
155 Austronesian across the Pacific provides important clues for this study in two ways. On the one
156 hand, that agri-food along the southeastern coast of mainland China may have provided important
157 base population growth, and on the other hand, that movement by sea is linked to resources,
158 population, cultural recognition, trade, and seafaring technology are all closely linked (P. S.
159 Bellwood et al. 1995).

160 The study will address the issue of cultural identity and the choice of direction of movement
161 through water:

- 162 1. What might be the cultural identity that initially causes movement at sea to occur?
- 163 2. Do people prefer the sea or the land during ongoing movement?
- 164 3. What kinds of different cultural landscape identities are reflected in this choice of sea and
165 land directions?

166 The study attempts to answer the influences and tendencies in the process of land and sea
167 movement through methodological construction.

168 The scope of the study starts from the Yangtze River Delta, which is the base of food
169 domestication, and involves the southeast coast of China, Southeast Asia, and the Phillipines. The
170 research will be considered in two diffusion directions, land and sea. The study is based on site
171 locations provided by archaeology and genetics, including Liangzhu, Liangdao, Keqitoutu,
172 Fugotun, Dabukeng, Fengbutou, Shenwan, ManBac, An Son, and Andarayan sites (Figure 4).

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174 **Figure 4** – Study area and direction of sea-land movement (author's own drawing,
175 base map courtesy of ArcGIS Pro)

A Three-tier Model of Maritime Movement

177 The ArcGIS Pro combines geospatial and textual attributes to effectively digitise sites from
 178 archaeology, linguistics and genetics. Least-Cost Model is used to analyse environmental factors
 179 and simulate more accessible areas, and is achieved through three main tools: path distance,
 180 corridor analysis, and cost paths.

181 The 'Path Distance' tool, which calculates the cost (physical effort, time, money, etc.) of moving
 182 between start and stop points on a raster surface, and which is able to take into account the
 183 horizontal and vertical aspects of the movement. The 'Corridor Analysis' tool, which is used to
 184 generate the ideal corridors for movement between the starting and stopping points. Corridors are
 185 an important type of discussion in this study, and 'corridors' or 'regions' are more in line with the
 186 real characteristics of human movement. The 'Cost Path' tool is used to generate a path that is
 187 optimal for movement. 'Paths provide clearer contrast and visibility in large-scale analyses. It
 188 should be noted that a single shortest movement 'path' is not the result needed for this paper, but
 189 it can be used to analyse directional shifts in movement and provide clues for subsequent cultural
 190 interpretations.

191 Method 1: Move on Land

192 Before constructing the model for land movement, it needs to be made clear that the marine
 193 raster data are not included in the calculations and the model will discuss land movement only.
 194 The base data consist of a digital elevation model and site points (Figure 5d). The digital elevation
 195 model is derived from raw 90 m resolution elevation data provided by the National Center for Public
 196 Science Data in Basic Disciplines (<https://www.gscloud.cn/>). Due to the large study area, the base
 197 data with a resolution of 10,000 metres (Fig. 5a), as well as the slope (Fig. 5b) and direction of
 198 slope (Fig. 5c) were used in the calculation process.

199 The environment in which land movement occurs requires consideration of horizontal and
 200 vertical factors. Horizontal factors may be the resistance created by factors such as forests and
 201 meadows, or the attraction of easier access created by roads (Figure 6). Vertical influences are
 202 used to express the amount of energy consumed by humans when travelling up or down a hill, and
 203 the angular thresholds vary for different modes of transport.

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205 (a) Digital Elevation Model

(b) Slope

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(c) Slope Direction (d) Heritage Sites
Figure 5 – Basic data for land movement modelling

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Figure 6 – Horizontal and vertical factors in land movement modelling (source: ArcGIS Pro)

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For the land movement calculations, firstly, the Path Distance tool was used to analyse the Path Distance data and the Backtracking Raster data from each site to the whole study area. Secondly, the 'corridor' tool was used to analyse the 'path distance data' and 'backward raster data' from each site to the whole study area. Secondly, the 'corridor analysis' tool was used to obtain the preferred area of movement. Finally, the shortest movement paths were visualised using the 'cost path' tool (Figure 7).

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Figure 7 – Least-cost modelling of land movement

220 The study analysed the minimum movement corridor and the shortest movement path from the
 221 food domestication base in the Yangtze River Delta (with the Liangzhu site as the starting point)
 222 to the southeastern coast of Fujian (with the Keqitoutou site in Pingtan as the target point), the coasts
 223 of Guangdong, Hong Kong and Macao (with the Sham Wan site in Hong Kong as the target point),
 224 and the coasts of Southeast Asia (with the Man Bac and An Son sites in Vietnam as the target point)
 225 (Fig. 8). Two things can be observed:

- 226 1. In addition to the least-cost corridor and path, there are always also a low-cost areas to
 227 the south of it. The paths are all close to the coast, which is not the shortest Euclidean
 228 distance between two points, but travelling through mountains obviously leads to
 229 increased costs.
- 230 2. Combined with the hilly landscape of the south-east coast of Asia, it can be judged that
 231 the more suitable areas for access are the coastal areas with flatter terrain, so the results
 232 of this part of the analysis are more reasonable in the macro-level judgement.

233 Then it would be discussed that what will happened if ancient people go along the coast.

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235 (a) from Liangzhu to Keqitoutou

(b) from Liangzhu to Sham Wan

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(c) from Liangzhu to Man Bac

(d) from Liangzhu to An Son

237 **Figure 8** – Results of least-cost modelling of land movement. Least-cost corridor
 238 and path (a) from Liangzhu to Keqitoutou, (b) from Liangzhu to Sham Wan, (c) from
 239 Liangzhu to Man Bac, (d) from Liangzhu to An Son
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241 **Method 2: Move on Coast**

242 Modelling of coastal movement will integrate land and sea parameters. In terms of basic data,
243 the digital elevation model, slope, and slope direction data from the land movement model are
244 followed. In terms of method flow, the calculation of coastal movement is similar to that of land
245 movement, using path distance data and backtracking raster data to obtain the minimum
246 movement corridor and the shortest movement path (Figure 9).

247 The difference is that the model introduces a digital elevation of the ocean surface for
248 participation in the cost modelling (Figure 10). In this model, the ocean is treated as a flat surface,
249 but other environmental data have not been added to the model for the purpose of determining the
250 human cost relationship of moving from land to sea.

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252 **Figure 9** – Least-cost modelling of coast movement

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254 **Figure 10** – Adding raster values to the ocean surface for coastal movement
255 calculations

256 From the perspective of combining land and ocean, the study similarly analysed the minimum
257 movement corridor and the shortest movement path from the Yangtze River Delta to reach the
258 southeast coast of Fujian, the coasts of Guangdong, Hong Kong and Macao, and the coasts of
259 Southeast Asia. The results of the analyses found that:

- 260 1. When the ocean surface raster was added to the calculation, the movement paths all
261 chose to use the ocean as the corridor (Figure 11). This has similarities with
262 archaeologists' proposal that the ocean represents a rich resource and faster passage
263 route (P. Bellwood 1979).

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2. Survival of coastal tribes by harvesting marine resources and safe maritime movement within a certain range can be seen as an inevitable development, especially when shipbuilding technology provided the tools for navigation.

Therefore, analysing the marine environment and identifying the direction of navigation is the next focus to be discussed, and the next section will introduce the marine environment to discuss the influencing factors and models of movement across the sea.

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(a) from Liangzhu to Keqitou

(b) from Liangzhu to Sham Wan

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(c) from Liangzhu to Man Bac

(d) from Liangzhu to An Son

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Figure 11 – Results of least-cost modelling of coastal movement, grey areas are ocean rasters. Least-cost corridor and path (a) from Liangzhu to Keqitou, (b) from Liangzhu to Sham Wan, (c) from Liangzhu to Man Bac, (d) from Liangzhu to An Son

277 **Method 3: Move on Sea**

278 The land raster will be removed before constructing the marine movement model, which only
 279 discusses movement at sea. The base data consists of site points distributed over the sea islands,
 280 with data on the marine environment, and time data (Figure 12).

281 Whether or not there are navigational instruments, 'time', more than 'space', can help in the
 282 movement of the oceans. Sailors use time to determine speed and distance, and in combination
 283 with constellations, sun angles, etc., direction and angle can be obtained (D. H. Lewis 1964).
 284 Therefore, seasonal variations are also important parameters in the modelling of ocean
 285 movements.

286 Unlike the influence of horizontal and vertical factors of topography on land movement, the
 287 ocean movement model mainly considers the combined influence of wind (wind direction and wind
 288 speed), ocean current (direction and speed of water flow), and ship (direction and speed of
 289 navigation) among the horizontal influencing factors. This study mainly uses wind data to construct
 290 the basic ocean movement model.

291 The wind data were obtained from the publicly available Pacific Maritime Laboratory
 292 (<http://apdrc.soest.hawaii.edu/las86>) wind environment u and v vector data for January and August
 293 2000 and processed by the ArcGIS Pro platform into usable wind direction and speed data (Figure
 294 13).

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296 **Figure 12 – Least-cost modelling of sea movement**

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298 (a) Wind direction of 1 Jan 2000

(b) Wind speed of 1 Jan 2000

(c) Wind direction of 1 Aug 2000

(d) Wind speed of 1 Aug 2000

Figure 13 – Wind direction and speed data

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The study analysed the movement from the Yangtze River Delta to the southeast coast of Fujian, the coasts of Guangdong, Hong Kong and Macao, and the coasts of Southeast Asia with and without the use of marine environmental data. At the same time, since the coast of Fujian is an area where land and ocean movements are differentiated, the movements from Pingtan to the coasts of Guangdong, Hong Kong and Macao, the coasts of South-East Asia, and the Philippines were also analysed in winter and summer (Figs. 14 and 15).

The results of the analyses found that, on the one hand, the model set up with environmental data has a more complex shift in the direction of movement, but the specific movement needs to be further verified; on the other hand, the movement corridors in winter versus summer show a more pronounced change in the area close to the coast, and the changes in these routes will largely affect the choice of the ancient people to land on the island.

(a) from Liangzhu to Keqiuou

(b) from Liangzhu to Sham Wan

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(c) from Liangzhu to Man Bac

(d) from Liangzhu to An Son

Figure 14 – Results of least-cost modelling of sea movement. Least-cost corridor and path (a) from Liangzhu to Kequtou, (b) from Liangzhu to Sham Wan, (c) from Liangzhu to Man Bac, (d) from Liangzhu to An Son

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Figure 15 – Differences paths of sea movement models in different parameters

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Discussion

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Cultural identity and maritime movement

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From the Yangtze River Delta to the Pingtan area, the three-layer movement model of 'land, coast, and sea' proposed in this study shows different movement channels, but all of them are found to be very close to the site of human remains on Liangdao Island, which is 8,300 years old.

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Sites excavated by geneticists on Ryo Island point to the way in which Austronesian thus left the southeastern coast of mainland China and spread further into the Pacific Ocean (Ko et al. 2014)(Figure 16). Archaeologist Lewis's theory and practice of navigation without navigational aids also confirms that even if the direction of movement at sea is not clear, it is possible to correct the

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331 direction and eventually reach the target island by entering the visible area of the island (D. H.
332 Lewis 1964).

333 Liangdao is a small island of about 1400 metres in length and 250 metres in width, which is
334 inconspicuous when placed in the vast ocean. In order to simulate the real situation as much as
335 possible, the present study introduced factors such as the high point of Liangdao, 63 m, and the
336 curvature of the earth into the visual analysis, and found that Liangdao appeared in the visible area
337 moving from north to south, both on land and along the coast, a condition that also provided
338 important clues (Figs. 17 and 18).

339 Vision is an important organ for human cognition of the landscape. The paths simulated in this
340 study overlap with the site, and on the one hand, it can be surmised that vision provided an
341 important role in early human spatial movement, and that the relationship between culture and
342 vision has influenced the way humans move to a certain extent; or at least, it can be surmised that
343 geographic elements that serve as prominent signposts for wayfinding will be one of the next steps
344 in conducting early human spatial movement simulations.

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346 **Figure 15** – The north to south distribution of Austronesian and the important role
347 of Liangdao (Ko et al. 2014)

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Figure 15 – The simulated route of movement passes right through Liangdao, and Liangdao's visible range appears in the simulated sea and land movement routes

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Figure 16 – Location of Liangdao

353 **Role, limitations, development of methodological models**

354 This paper constructs a three-layered 'land-coast-sea' movement model that links land and
 355 ocean movements in digital space, which will help to explain the cultural phenomena behind the
 356 domestication of rice on land, the diffusion across the sea, and the dissemination of language by
 357 ancient humans.

358 The method is a framework model, premised on a more macro-level view of human origins and
 359 dispersal, and as such the method is not focussed on a particular historical event, but historical
 360 events can be added as textual attributes to the framework model for validation and interpretation.

361 From the perspective of the international academic community, with reference to the
362 Mediterranean region (Gheorghide and Spencer 2024; Gal, Saaroni, and Cvikel 2023; Perttola
363 2022; Alberti 2018; Safadi 2016; Leidwanger 2013), which is more mature in the study of offshore
364 movement, from the basic single wind element modelling to the complex model building with more
365 factors superimposed, from the two-dimensional to the multi-dimensional spatial analysis, from the
366 Euclidean distances to the simulation of paths combined with the real environmental changes.
367 Methodological iterations and upgrades are a general rule of development in the study of maritime
368 movements.

369 In this study, the subjective role of the sailing vessel and the sailor is not taken into account
370 (although it is one of the most important conditions), and oceanic movements are considered as
371 individuals drifting with the sea breeze, such that they also include more primitive ways of moving,
372 such as the drifting of a single person.

373 In summary, from the perspective of methodological development, the methodological model
374 in this paper, although preliminary, limited, and exploratory, is the foundation and prerequisite for
375 the further construction of a more realistic and complex model of the ancient maritime environment.
376 At the same time, the iterative direction of the model has become clearer due to the fact that there
377 are already mature cases in different sea areas for reference. In the more complex and high-
378 precision ocean movement, the direction and speed of wind, the direction and speed of ocean
379 currents, and the navigational performance of different types of vessels will be taken into account
380 to achieve a more accurate simulation of ocean movement, which is also the direction of the
381 model's further development in the future, and is expected to ultimately achieve the reproduction
382 of early human cross-sea navigation.

383

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386

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391

Conflict of interest disclosure

392 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest
393 in relation to the content of the article.

394

Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability

395 Data are available online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13592103>; Luo Hongpeng, 2024

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